

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF VECTRAN-STITCHED COMPOSITES: NUMERICAL MODELING AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

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1 Introduction

Impact loading may induce delamination in composite materials. In the area prone to this type of loading, 3D-composites are desirable instead of 2D-composites. One of the 3D composites presently considered is stitched composites. Stitched composites can be manufactured by resin transfer moulding (RTM) process, whereby epoxy resin is applied onto the stacks of stitched fabrics at high temperature. Vacuum environment can also be applied, and the process is called VaRTM (Vacuum-assisted Resin Transfer Moulding). As a result, stitched composites exhibit improved through-thickness strength, i.e. interlaminar strength, because stitch yarns can impede delamination.

Fig. 1. (a) Carbon/epoxy composites stitched with Vectran thread, (b) stitch used in present research has a spacing of 3mm and pitch of 3 mm

Understanding the mechanical behaviour of stitched composites is essential prior to the application of stitched composites in the airframe. The basic thermo-mechanical properties should be obtained to streamline the material selection during design process. However, material testing is somewhat costly and time consuming. To complement the test, analysis of the mechanical properties is of paramount importance. There are several numerical

and analytical models used to predict the properties of stitched composites. Dickinson *et al.* [1] proposed a two-dimensional unit cell model with star pattern to evaluate the properties of trans-laminar-reinforced (TLR) composites. Grassi *et al.* [2] proposed two models; the first model was used to evaluate elastic constants and local stress distribution, while the second model was used to study the interlaminar shear stresses. Heß *et al.* [3] proposed a finite element unit-cell model to estimate tensile and compressive properties of stitched composites. The aim of the present paper is to propose the use of homogenization technique (based on asymptotic expansion homogenization) in predicting the mechanical properties of Vectran-stitched composites. Homogenization method can produce accurate result efficiently. The periodicity in homogenization method is also guaranteed.

The composite used in present investigation is carbonT800SC-24kf/epoxy XNR6813, and it is structurally stitched by using Vectran[®] thread (400 denier). The stitch density of current specimen is 11.1/cm² (stitch pitch = 3 mm; stitch spacing = 3 mm). A simplified 3D model of stitched composites based on the observation of their mesostructural constituents is proposed. The model consists of multi-axial tows, straight resin channel and stitch thread. The model does not include undulation, which is commonly found in stitched composites. The undulation, which give rise to the complexity of architecture and formulation, will be considered in the future. The predicted elastic constants obtained by homogenization method is validated by uniaxial tensile test of stitched composites.

2 Homogenization theory

A brief review of homogenization theory is given in this section. Homogenization theory is developed

from partial differential equations with varying coefficients [4-5]. The theory assumes two conditions:

- the field variables vary on multiple scales due to the existence of microstructures
- the microstructure is spatially periodic

In this method, precise boundary conditions imposed to the microscopic model yield a very accurate prediction of equivalent elastic constants and local stresses. Stress – strain relationship can be written as follows

$$\sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon = E_{ijkl}^\varepsilon \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i^\varepsilon}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j^\varepsilon}{\partial x_i} \right) - \alpha_{kl}^\varepsilon \Delta T \right] \quad (1)$$

where E_{ijkl}^ε is elastic tensor, α_{kl}^ε is coefficient of thermal expansion and ΔT is temperature difference. Superscript ε represents the ratio between macroscopic (x) and microscopic (y) scale ($\varepsilon = x/y$). Eq. (1) can be solved by the principle of virtual work by defining the real and virtual displacements of $u_i^\varepsilon(x)$ and $v_i(x,y)$.

$$\int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} E_{ijkl}^\varepsilon \left(\frac{\partial u_k^\varepsilon}{\partial x_i} - \alpha_{kl}^\varepsilon \Delta T \right) \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma_i} t_i v_i d\Gamma \quad (2)$$

where t_i is surface tractions.

Solution for $u_i^\varepsilon(x)$ must satisfy the macroscopic and microscopic dimensions. Thus, asymptotic expansion of displacement is introduced as follows

$$u^\varepsilon(x) = u^0(x, y) + \varepsilon u^1(x, y) + O(x, y) \quad (3)$$

The higher order terms $O(x,y)$ are omitted in this regard. The displacements and stress tensors are written as follow

$$u^\varepsilon(x) = u^0(x, y) + \varepsilon u^1(x, y) \quad (4)$$

$$u_i^0(x, y) = u_i^0(x) \quad (5)$$

$$u_i^1(y) = -\chi_i^{kl}(y) \frac{\partial u_k^0(x, y)}{\partial x_i} - \Psi_i(y) \Delta T \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma^\varepsilon(x) = \sigma^0(x, y) \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^0(x, y) = \left(E_{ijkl}(x, y) - E_{ijpm}(x, y) \frac{\partial \chi_p^{kl}(x, y)}{\partial y_m} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_k^0(x)}{\partial x_i} - E_{ijkl}(x, y) \frac{\partial \Psi_k(x, y)}{\partial y_l} - E_{ijkl}(x, y) \alpha_k \Delta T$$

where χ_i^{kl} and Ψ_k are characteristic displacements.

The characteristics displacements can be calculated using following formulae

$$\int_{\mathbb{Y}} \left(E_{ijkl}(x, y) - E_{ijpm} \frac{\partial \chi_p^{kl}}{\partial y_m} \right) \frac{\partial v_i(y)}{\partial y_j} dY = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\int_{\mathbb{Y}} \left(E_{ijkl} \alpha_{kl} \Delta T - \frac{\partial \Psi_k}{\partial y_l} \right) \frac{\partial v_i(y)}{\partial y_i} dY = 0 \quad (10)$$

In three-dimensional formulation, six sets of problem associated with $\chi_i^{kl}(k, l=1,2,3)$ must be obtained considering the symmetry. Macroscopic homogenized elastic constants can therefore be defined as

$$E_{ijkl}^0 = \frac{1}{|\mathbb{Y}|} \int_{\mathbb{Y}} \left(E_{ijkl}(x, y) - E_{ijpm} \frac{\partial \chi_p^{kl}}{\partial y_m} \right) \quad (11)$$

3 Numerical Modeling

3.1 Micromodel

In the numerical modeling, it is essential to examine the constituents of stitched composites by microscopic observation. Stitched composites consist of fiber tow, resin pocket (or resin channel) and stitch thread. In this part, micromodel is used to evaluate the properties of fiber tow. The fibers in fiber tow are commonly arranged in random manner. The randomness can actually be idealized by representative volume element (RVE) of hexagonal model (Fig. 2). Finite element model contains 896 elements (hexahedron 20-node) and 4713 nodes was built. In this preliminary investigation using homogenization, fiber volume fraction (V_f) of the pack is selected to be 50%. Mechanical and thermal properties of carbon fiber T800SC-24kf (produced by Toray Industries, Inc.) are $E_{11} = 294$ GPa, $E_{22} = E_{33} = 6.5$ GPa, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 18.2$ GPa, $G_{23} = 6.5$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.32$, $\nu_{23} = 0.41$, $\alpha_{11} = -7.8 \times 10^{-7}$ /°C, $\alpha_{22} =$

$\alpha_{33} = 8.1 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Properties of resin epoxy XNR/6813 are $E = 8.96 \text{ GPa}$, $G = 3.45 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu = 0.35$, $\alpha = 6.45 \times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The micromodel was used to calculate the elastic properties of fiber tow. The finite element model of hexagonal pack was built using *MSC.Patran 2008*, whilst the FEM-based homogenization method was developed using *Fortran 90*. Results of homogenization method are compared with the Rule of Mixtures and Halpin-Tsai theory.

Fig. 2. Micromodel of hexagonal RVE used to evaluate fiber tow properties

3.2 Mesomodel

At mesoscale, fiber tow, resin pocket (or resin channel) and stitch thread are explicitly built. Fig. 3(a) shows the constituents of stitched composites, whilst Fig. 3(b) shows the top view of unit cell of stitched composite. Two types of resin pocket are found during microscopic observation. They are eye-let and channel types. In present model, channel model is chosen for its simplicity. The lay-up of stitched composites is $[-45/90/+45/0_2/-45/90_2/+45/0]_s$. The lay-up is simplified into four layers consisting of 0° ply (30%), 90° ply (30%), 45° ply (20%) and -45° ply (20%). The FE mesomodel consisting of these four plies was built using *MSC.Patran 2008*. The number of element is 19200, while the number of nodes is 83633. Fig. 3(c) shows the FE model.

Fig. 3. (a) Top view of one section in stitched composite, (b) Top view of finite element mesomodel of stitched composite, (c) orthogonal view of FE mesomodel

4 Experimental

Monotonic tensile test was performed to obtain stress – strain curve. Universal Testing Machine Instron 8802 with capacity of 100 kN was used. Strain measurement was carried out using uniaxial strain gages with gage length of 5 mm (KYOWA). Three samples of stitched composite with stitch density of $11.1/\text{cm}^2$ were tested, and tensile modulus (E_x) and Poisson's ratio (ν_{xy}) were obtained. Each sample has dimension of 200 mm (length), 25 mm (width) and 4.1 mm (thickness). The test was conducted with the loading rate of 1 mm/min. Temperature setting was 23°C .

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Fiber tow properties

Table 1 shows fiber tow elastic moduli obtained by homogenization method in comparison with Rule of Mixture (R.O.M) and Halpin-Tsai theory. Results of homogenization method generally agree with the micromechanics approaches. Halpin-Tsai seems to overestimate the transverse moduli. On the other hand, shear stiffnesses obtained by homogenization are larger than those of R.O.M and Halpin-Tsai. The differences are

mostly affected by the choice of fiber packing type. The results of present homogenization method were then used to calculate the mechanical properties of stitched composites using mesomodel.

Table 1. Fiber tow properties (V_{f-tow} of 50%)

Properties	Homogenization (present)	R.O.M.	Halpin- Tsai
E_x (GPa)	142.99	151.48	151.48
E_y (GPa)	8.94	7.53	31.82
E_z (GPa)	8.52	7.53	31.82
G_{xy} (GPa)	12.06	5.80	7.52
G_{xz} (GPa)	12.06	5.80	7.52
G_{yz} (GPa)	7.78	5.80	3.45
ν_{xy}	0.350	0.335	0.335
ν_{xz}	0.340	0.335	0.335
ν_{yz}	0.430	0.380	0.380

5.2 Stitched composite properties

Table 2 shows the full-set of mechanical properties of stitched composites evaluated using homogenization method. Fig. 4 shows the typical stress – strain curves of stitched composites. The tensile modulus E_x and Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} were calculated from the stress and strain data between $\epsilon = 0.1\%$ and $\epsilon = 0.3\%$.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of Vectran-stitched composite obtained by homogenization method

Properties	Magnitude
E_x (GPa)	48.35
E_y (GPa)	48.34
E_z (GPa)	12.09
G_{xy} (GPa)	13.66
G_{xz} (GPa)	6.67
G_{yz} (GPa)	6.67
ν_{xy}	0.10
ν_{xz}	0.38
ν_{yz}	0.38

Table 3 shows the comparison of tensile modulus E_x and Poisson's ratio ν_{xy} between experiment and homogenization method. It is found that E_x obtained by homogenization method is considered to be in a good agreement with that of experiment. The difference is around 4.26%. However, ν_x of homogenization method is considerably lower than the experimental result. The difference may be caused by the idealization of the fiber

tow into the straight block (i.e. fiber undulation is excluded). Other reason is that the resin pocket is modeled as a 'channel' instead of eye-let. In this regard, volume fraction of tow may contribute to the difference.

A new model will be developed to include fiber undulation, whereby the properties within a fiber tow would conform the fiber waviness, and eye-let pocket.

Fig. 4. Stress – strain curves of Vectran-stitched composites under tensile loading

Table 3. Stitched composite properties

Properties	Homogenization	Experiment
E_x (GPa)	48.35	50.5
ν_{xy}	0.10	0.35

6 Conclusion

Homogenization method based on asymptotic expansion is developed to predict mechanical properties of stitched composites. Two scales of investigation were performed: micromechanics simulation to predict fiber tow properties, and mesomechanics simulation to predict stitched composite properties. Tensile test was also performed to validate the numerical results. It is found that homogenization method is accurate and efficient in predicting the tensile modulus.

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